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Emulating Public Opinion: A Proof-of-Concept of AI-Generated Synthetic Survey Responses for the Chilean Case

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Abstract

Large Language Models (LLMs) offer promising avenues for methodological and applied innovations in survey research by using synthetic respondents to emulate human answers and behaviour, potentially mitigating measurement and representation errors. However, the extent to which LLMs recover aggregate item distributions remains uncertain and downstream applications risk reproducing social stereotypes and biases inherited from training data. We evaluate the reliability of LLM-generated synthetic survey responses against ground-truth human responses from a Chilean public opinion probabilistic survey. Specifically, we benchmark 128 prompt-model-question triplets, generating 189,696 synthetic profiles, and pool performance metrics (i.e., accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score) in a meta-analysis across 128 question-subsample pairs to test for biases along key sociodemographic

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dimensions. The evaluation spans OpenAI’s GPT family and o-series reasoning models, as well as Llama and Qwen checkpoints. Three results stand out. First, synthetic responses achieve excellent performance on trust items (F1-score and accuracy > 0.90). Second, GPT-4o, GPT-4o-mini and Llama 4 Maverick perform comparably on this task. Third, synthetic-human alignment is highest among respondents aged 45-59. Overall, LLM-based synthetic samples approximate responses from a probabilistic sample, though with substantial item-level heterogeneity. Capturing the full nuance of public opinion remains challenging and requires careful calibration and additional distributional tests to ensure algorithmic fidelity and reduce errors.

Keywords: synthetic samples; survey data; LLMs; benchmark; public opinion

1 Introduction

Traditional public opinion surveys face a number of challenges and risks related to measurement and representation dimensions, including, for example, coverage error due to incomplete frames and hard-to-reach groups, sampling error resulting from finite samples and complex designs, nonresponse error stemming from low participation and interview fatigue, measurement error introduced by questionnaire wording, and processing errors in coding and post-survey adjustments, among others (Groves, 1989; Groves and Lyberg, 2010; Weisberg, 2005). These errors could be amplified by substantial financial, human, and logistical demands, such as time spent on instrument design, piloting, and fieldwork that often forces a cost-quality trade-off that may distort population inferences. Consequently, there is a growing demand in the social sciences and market research for methods that reduce burden and cost while maintaining and improving overall data quality.

Against this backdrop, Large Language Models (LLMs), trained extensively on vast and diverse data, emerge as promising alternatives for new research possibilities and applied research, including handling the abovementioned survey research limitations and measurement and representation errors. Indeed, recent advances in generative artificial intelligence (AI) suggest LLMs could serve for a number of classification tasks, including the creation of synthetic samples, providing simulated responses reflective of broader societal attitudes and behaviours (Argyle et al., 2023; Gilardi et al., 2023; González-Bustamante, 2024). The synthetic samples specifically may leverage the ability of LLMs to generate contextually informed responses based on individual-level demographic characteristics and attitudes, and, in this way, potentially emulate public opinion without direct interaction with human respondents. This methodological innovation opens new avenues for rapid data collection, experimentation with sensitive topics, and a deeper understanding of complex public opinion dynamics that complement or even partially

substitute for traditional surveys.

Thus, the primary objective of this working paper is to evaluate the effectiveness and reliability of LLM-generated synthetic survey responses in reflecting real-world public opinion in Chile. Specifically, we aim to assess the predictive accuracy of a number of state-of-the-art private and open-source LLMs by comparing their synthetic respondents against human probabilistic responses.¹ Furthermore, we examine the impact of incorporating a variety of contextual information, including demographic and attitudinal variables, on the predictive performance of the models. In doing so, we contribute to the understanding of the feasibility and potential downstream applications of synthetic survey methodologies and LLMs in public opinion research.

2 From Synthetic Data to Synthetic Publics: LLMs in Public Opinion Research

Synthetic data have a long tradition in the social sciences, initially used to deal with nonresponse using multiple imputation (Rubin, 1993; see also Little, 1993; Little and Rubin, 1987; Raghunathan et al., 2003). However, while the current research in synthetic data is mainly motivated by harvesting considerable data to train machine learning models, some government agencies are exploring these approaches to broaden public access to their resources (Drechsler and Haensch, 2023). Indeed, there is potential related to privacy-preserving and cost-efficient substitutes for microdata, aiming to reproduce joint distributions without exposing individual, sensitive records. Although there are several applications, from patient information and health records (Choi et al., 2018; Yahi et al., 2017) to environmental monitoring (Allken et al., 2019), all of them share a common goal: the synthetic data must be similar to the results obtained using actual data (Drechsler and Haensch, 2023). In this sense, synthetic data may not be merely a way to deal with missingness or privacy concerns for survey-oriented applications; when properly constructed and validated, they can act as stand-ins for hard-to-obtain samples, enabling faster iteration and lower-cost implementation.

A number of early applications originated from techniques developed to address class imbalance and small- N constraints. Methods like Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) and its variants showed that augmenting minority classes can reduce the

¹By a synthetic respondent, we mean an AI-generated persona used to simulate a survey participant. We create these personas by giving an LLM basic traits, as we further detail in the method section. Then, we ask it to answer as if it were that person.

accuracy paradox² and improve sensitivity in rare event settings.³ Subsequent research generalised this intuition to broader data scarcity, showing that generators which preserve covariance structure and local dependencies (e.g., optimised multivariable Kernel Density Estimation, KDE, for small biomedical datasets or fuzzy diffusions via k -nearest neighbours) can expand datasets while maintaining multivariate relationships (Fowler et al., 2020; Sivakumar et al., 2022). For survey research, the relevance of these advances lies less in their original domains than in the transferable principle that credible synthetic data must respect the joint distribution of key covariates rather than merely reproduce marginals.

Modern methods have been increasingly tackling the challenge of data scarcity and sparsity, moving beyond the focus on class distribution. Fowler et al. (2020), for example, developed a method using optimised multivariate KDE to generate entire synthetic populations from small biomedical datasets. Their objective was not to balance classes but to prevent overfitting by meticulously replicating the complex, correlated covariance of the original data, thereby creating a sufficiently large and representative dataset for modelling where none existed before. This focus on the small data problem is also evident in the work of Sivakumar et al. (2022), who created the kNN Mega-Trend Diffusion (kNNMTD) method. This approach is agnostic to the learning task, whether regression or classification, and is designed explicitly for tiny datasets. Indeed, the kNNMDT method is able to generate plausible synthetic data that faithfully maintains the original data correlation structure by applying a fuzzy-set-based information diffusion technique locally via k -nearest neighbours, preventing overestimation.

Parallel advances in deep generative modelling, such as Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs; see Goodfellow et al., 2014) and diffusion models, extended synthetic data beyond tabular settings to sequential and textual modalities.⁴ Beyond their use in time series (see de Souza et al., 2023) and text (see Tolba et al., 2021), GANs have been effectively applied to augment structured survey data in the social sciences. Ruiz-Gándara

²Accuracy, as a classic machine learning indicator, reflects the proportion of correct predictions of a model in the test set, however, it could be misled by data imbalance because the model is predicting the majority class and is not able to identify underrepresented categories (González-Bustamante, 2023, 2025b).

³The foundational work in synthetic sampling, notably the SMOTE, was indeed primarily designed to mitigate class imbalance by generating examples for the minority class. SMOTE remains effective nowadays. For instance, de Blasio et al. (2022) demonstrated that it was important for transforming a model with zero sensitivity for detecting rare instances of municipal corruption into a viable tool for policy intervention. Without synthetic oversampling, their model failed to identify positive cases, a classic example of the accuracy paradox. Similarly, Walid et al. (2022) and Tchokote and Tagne (2025) found that advanced SMOTE variants were effective for enhancing model robustness and prediction accuracy in educational data mining and multimodal hate speech detection tasks, respectively.

⁴Moving beyond simple tabular data, for example, some techniques could generate synthetic instances in sparse regions of the feature space and assign a new label distribution by interpolating the ones of neighbouring instances (González et al., 2021). Other progress has been made in the integration of synthetic sampling and multimodal pipelines (see Tchokote and Tagne, 2025).

et al. (2025) demonstrated that GANs could generate synthetic survey responses that maintained the original data’s statistical behaviour, spurring the development of novel harmonic mean-based indices for quality evaluation. In addition, comparative studies have emphasised that quality matters more than quantity (de Souza et al., 2023), proposing evaluation frameworks that benchmark not only predictive accuracy, but also distributional similarity based on measures such as Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) and PCA-based (i.e., based on Principal Component Analysis) diagnostics (Fowler et al., 2020), along with correlation-preservation metrics such as Pairwise Correlation Difference (PCD; see Sivakumar et al., 2022).⁵

Against this methodological backdrop, a new strand evaluates LLMs directly as synthetic respondents. The core design emulates survey interviews by conditioning an LLM on respondent profiles based on demographics and, when available, attitudinal traits (Argyle et al., 2023; Kim and Lee, 2024). Evidence is mixed but promising: LLMs can recover aggregate distributions for specific items, reproduce well-known covariates-attitude associations, and display sensitivity to profile granularity and prompt wording (Argyle et al., 2023; Bisbee et al., 2024). Shrestha et al. (2024) explored the use of GPT-4 to generate synthetic data for policy surveys across diverse cultural contexts, reaching a reasonable aggregate alignment with human responses, however, they also uncovered systematic positive biases and cultural variability in the accuracy of synthetic data. Boelaert et al. (2025) indicated, on the other hand, that current models could hardly emulate human respondents because of machine bias. In sum, this mixed evidence highlights both the potential of LLMs to create large-scale synthetic data and the inherent risk of introducing biases that may be difficult to detect because of the intrinsic patterns from pretraining data and instruction tuning datasets (Geng et al., 2024; González-Bustamante, 2024).

Indeed, the risk for downstream applications based on LLMs could be associated with encoding social stereotypes or political biases, yielding subgroups distortions or directional tilt on contentious issues (Morris, 2025; Santurkar et al., 2023; Qu and Wang, 2024). For this reason, the level of algorithmic fidelity, which reflects how LLMs can replicate effectively socio-cultural contexts and nuanced viewpoints of subpopulations, is quite relevant (Argyle et al., 2023; Ma et al., 2025). In this sense, safeguarding algorithmic fidelity should motivate evaluation practices that move beyond headline accuracy by focusing on subgroups, evaluation of prompt perturbations (see Bisbee et al., 2024), among other innovative approaches. For survey emulation, validating the synthetic distribution against probabilistic samples should be considered as a starting point to test the quality of the AI-generated synthetic profiles.

⁵Alternative options for exploring the distribution are measures such as Earth-Mover’s Distance (EMD; see Boelaert et al., 2025; González-Bustamante, 2019; Lupu et al., 2017).

3 Methodology

3.1 Survey Emulation and Probabilistic Sample

For survey emulation and validation of the synthetic distribution, we rely on the probabilistic sample survey conducted by the Centro de Estudios Públicos (CEP) in Chile, widely recognised for its rigorous methodology and comprehensive coverage of sociodemographic and attitudinal variables. The CEP survey programme has served since 1986 as a barometer of public opinion on political and economic views, key societal concerns, and citizens’ evaluations of government performance and other major actors.

The target population of the CEP survey comprises residents aged 18 and older across Chile, excluding provinces classified as difficult to access by the National Statistics Institute (INE in Spanish), namely Easter Island, Palena, and Antarctica. The sample design is probabilistic, stratified by region and by urban-rural area, with random selection at three stages: block, household, and respondent. The instrument is a structured questionnaire incorporating programmed skip patterns, administered face-to-face using electronic devices such as tablets or smartphones to enhance accuracy and consistency in data collection. In addition, survey results are weighted and adjusted post-survey to account for selection probabilities and nonresponse, thereby correcting under- or over-representation of specific groups.

Specifically, we employed the probabilistic survey number 92, carried out between August 2 and September 12, 2024.⁶ This survey comprised 1,482 face-to-face interviews conducted across 127 Chilean municipalities, yielding a response rate of 61.3% from an initial sample of 2,416. The sample error was ± 2.8 with a 95% confidence interval.

3.2 LLMs, Prompting Strategies and Performance

We tested the performance of a number of state-of-the-art private and open-source LLMs. Our proof-of-concept included flagship OpenAI GPTs such as GPT-4o (2024-11-20), GPT-4o-mini (2024-07-18), GPT-4.5-preview (2025-02-27), GPT-4.1, 4.1-mini and 4.1-nano (2025-04-14), as well as reasoning models like o1-mini (2024-09-12) and o3-mini (2025-01-31). We also tested the latest Llama 4 Maverick (400B) and Scout (107B), Llama 3.3 (70B), Qwen 2.5 (32B) and Gemma 3 (12B).⁷

⁶We created the synthetic profiles by the end of April 2025. By that time, CEP number 92 was the latest released survey. Further information is available on <https://www.cepchile.cl/opinion-publica>.

⁷We tried to consider o1 (2024-12-17) and o4-mini (2025-04-16), however, being reasoning models, the tasks required considerable time. For future applications, Qwen 3 (0.6B, 1.7B, 4B, 8B, 14B, 30B, 32B and 235B), released the last week of April 2025, may be a suitable alternative. In addition, more recent models, such as GPT-5 or the novel, very first open-source OpenAI model GPT-OSS (20B and 120B), released in August 2025, should be good options. It is relevant to note that there are a variety of state-of-the-art closed and open-source flagship models developed by Anthropic, Bespoke Labs, DeepSeek-AI,

We employed two distinct prompting strategies to generate synthetic responses. The first strategy utilises exclusively demographic information (i.e., region, urban or rural area, age, sex, educational level, socioeconomic group, and occupation). The second one incorporates attitudinal dimensions, such as individuals’ political interests, ideological identification, and previous demographic characteristics. This dual approach enables us to investigate the effect of varying contextual information levels on the accuracy of LLMs. Therefore, we created 1,482 synthetic profiles per prompting strategy, which implies 38,532 synthetic profiles (1,482 respondent profiles \times 2 prompting strategies \times 13 LLMs) for the proof-of-concept, focusing on the question: “*According to the following scale, how would you rate the country’s current economic situation? Very bad, bad, neither good nor bad, good, very good.*”

We then benchmarked the LLMs’ predictive performance by estimating standard evaluation metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score (Biecek and Burzykowski, 2021; González-Bustamante, 2023, 2025b). We reduced the list of models for benchmarking based on the proof-of-concept indicators⁸ provided in the Appendix in order to conduct an error-rate analysis using the questions in Table 1 as ground-truth. Consequently, we tested GPT-4o (2024-11-20), GPT-4o-mini (2024-07-18), Llama 4 Maverick (400B), and Qwen 2.5 (32B), which involved the creation of 189,696 synthetic profiles (1,482 respondent profiles \times 2 prompting strategies \times 4 LLMs \times 16 ground-truth questions, including the proof-of-concept question and the expanded ones for benchmark).⁹ This implies that we have 128 observations for the prompting-LLM-question triplet.

3.3 Meta-Analysis of Bias

We focus GPT-4o-mini (2024-07-18) on 16 ground-truth questions crossed with eight sociodemographic subsamples to analyse potential bias in 128 combinations for the question-subsample pairs (16 questions \times 8 subsamples). The subsets were elaborated based on a number of relevant sociodemographic variables, including area (urban vs. rural), gender (female vs. male), and age groups (i.e., 18-29, 30-44, 45-59, and 60 and older). We focused on the F1-score, which is appropriate given that the items’ responses can be imbalanced, and then fit random-effects meta-regressions to separate sampling error from

Mistral, among other providers, that are worthy of trying (see González-Bustamante, 2025a).

⁸The goodness-of-prediction indicators of the proof-of-concept against economic perception did not show the best performance, however, as we will discuss in the results for the final benchmark, some model \times question pairs show relatively high performance with F1-scores above 0.9, particularly for questions related to trust. This suggests that there is considerable heterogeneity not only depending on the model but also in relation to the question.

⁹By a ground-truth question, we mean the human responses to a specific survey item from our reference probabilistic sample. We use this observed distribution as the benchmark to evaluate LLM-generated answers. This ground-truth is an empirical measure, not normative, and is subject to the survey sampling error indicated above.

Table 1: Expanded Ground-Truth Questions for Benchmark

Topic	Question
Economic perception	Do you think that in the next 12 months the economic situation in the country will improve, stay the same or get worse?
Economic perception	According to the following scale, how would you rate your current economic situation? Very bad, bad, neither good nor bad, good, very good.
Political perception	How would you rate the current political situation in Chile? Very bad, bad, neither good nor bad, good, very good.
Government approval	Regardless of your political position, do you approve or disapprove of the way President Gabriel Boric is leading the government? Approves, disapproves, neither approves nor disapproves.
Democracy	Which of the following statements do you most agree with? Democracy is always preferable, sometimes an authoritarian regime can be preferable, a democratic regime is the same as an authoritarian regime.
Trust	Can you tell me how much confidence you have in the Catholic Church? A lot of confidence, fairly confident, low confidence, no confidence.
Trust	Can you tell me how much confidence you have in the Armed Forces? A lot of confidence, fairly confident, low confidence, no confidence.
Trust	Can you tell me how much confidence you have in the courts of justice? A lot of confidence, fairly confident, low confidence, no confidence.
Trust	Can you tell me how much confidence you have in the written press? A lot of confidence, fairly confident, low confidence, no confidence.
Trust	Can you tell me how much confidence you have in the TV? A lot of confidence, fairly confident, low confidence, no confidence.
Trust	Can you tell me how much confidence you have in the police (Carabineros de Chile)? A lot of confidence, fairly confident, low confidence, no confidence.
Trust	Can you tell me how much confidence you have in the government? A lot of confidence, fairly confident, low confidence, no confidence.
Trust	Can you tell me how much confidence you have in the political parties? A lot of confidence, fairly confident, low confidence, no confidence.
Trust	Can you tell me how much confidence you have in Congress? A lot of confidence, fairly confident, low confidence, no confidence.
Trust	Can you tell me how much confidence you have in the radio? A lot of confidence, fairly confident, low confidence, no confidence.

between-synthetic heterogeneity.

Our meta-analysis proceeds incrementally. The first model only incorporated a binary variable for urban area, and then we incorporated the female variable, using male as the reference category. The third model incorporated the age groups using the younger group as a reference category. In all models, we include ground-truth questions as fixed effects, which absorb item-specific baseline differences (i.e., wording and context effects). Formally, the equation for a question-subsample pair (q, s) is as follows, considering $G = 16$ as the number of questions benchmarked:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F1_{[q,s]} = & \alpha + \beta_1 \text{urban-area}_s + \beta_2 \text{female}_s + \sum_{k=2}^K \gamma_k \text{age-group}_{[k,s]} \\
 & + \sum_{g=2}^G \delta_g \text{ground-truth}_{[g,q]} + u_{[q,s]} + \varepsilon_{[q,s]}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

4 Results

4.1 Error-Rate Analysis

Figure 1: Goodness-of-Prediction Metrics of Synthetic Samples Against Ground-Truth Probabilistic Sample

Note. Accuracy reports the proportion of synthetic samples aligned with the probabilistic reference sample. Precision represents the fraction of predicted positives that are correct, and recall indicates the proportion of actual positives identified. The F1-score is the harmonic measure that combines both precision and recall.

We not only estimated the standard evaluation metrics (i.e., accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score) summarised in [Figure 1](#), but also the arithmetic mean (PPI) and the geometric mean (GPI) based on the evaluation metrics. PPI provides an intuitive sense of overall quality across different performance metrics, while GPI balances across metrics by penalising weakness in one of the metrics. These metrics provide a comprehensive assessment of each model’s ability to emulate actual respondents accurately and range from 0.696 to 0.919 for the top 15 model-question pairs available in the [Appendix](#), which is a significant improvement in comparison with the original proof-of-concept.

Two general patterns emerge from the evidence. First, the synthetic responses on trust demonstrated excellent performance, with F1-scores and accuracy even above 0.90. Second, the performance of GPT-4o (2024-11-20) and GPT-4o-mini (2024-07-18) is quite similar and comparable to Llama 4 Maverick (400B). [Figure 2](#) presents boxplots grouped by models for accuracy and F1-score, which confirm the advantages of these models in comparison with Qwen 2.5 (32B).

Figure 2: Accuracy and F1-Score Across Models

Note. Accuracy reports the proportion of synthetic samples aligned with the probabilistic reference sample. The F1-score, on the other hand, combines precision (i.e., fraction of predicted positives that are correct) and recall (i.e., proportion of actual positives identified).

4.2 Bias Analysis

[Table 2](#) presents the results of our random-effects meta-regressions using the 128 valid question-subsample pairs and the logit F1-score as the dependent variable. We only found a positive, significant coefficient for the age group from 45 to 59 years old (OR = 1.145, $\gamma = 0.136$, 95% CI [0.056, 0.215], $p \leq 0.001$), resulting in a 3.4 percentage points average improvement in the F1-score in comparison with the younger group. This evidence suggests that the synthetic sample is closer to human respondents in this group. In addition, the absence of significant negative coefficients could be interpreted as a sign of the absence of bias, however, this should require further exploration of the distributions using, for example, EMD or other similar measures ([Boelaert et al., 2025](#)).

Table 2: Mixed-Effects Regressions of F1-Scores from Synthetic Samples Against Ground-Truth Probabilistic Sample

	Model I	Model II	Model III
Reference category: Rural area			
Urban area	0.025 (0.029)	0.019 (0.030)	0.054 (0.006)
Reference category: Male			
Female		-0.030 (0.031)	0.006 (0.035)
Reference category: Age 18-29			
Age 30-44			0.047 (0.041)
Age 45-59			0.136*** (0.041)
Age 60 or older			0.020 (0.038)
Constant	0.055 (0.045)	0.061 (0.045)	0.026 (0.047)
Ground-truth FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
N	128	128	128
τ^2	0.007 (0.002)	0.007 (0.002)	0.007 (0.002)
τ	0.084	0.084	0.081
I^2	44.47%	44.22%	42.45%
R^2	0.989	0.989	0.990
AIC	-68.589	-65.022	-64.099
BIC	-19.817	-13.713	-5.297

Note. Table entries report coefficient estimates and standard errors in parentheses. AIC: Akaike information criterion; BIC: Bayesian information criterion; FE: fixed-effects.

* $p \leq 0.1$; ** $p \leq 0.05$; *** $p \leq 0.01$.

The moderators explained 99% of the between-synthetic heterogeneity, and there is a low residual heterogeneity ($\tau^2 = 0.007$, $I^2 = 42.45\%$, in model III). This is because the ground-truth questions fixed effects have a significant impact on the models, especially those related to trust variables against the country's current economic situation question as a reference category.¹⁰ For example, trust in political parties (OR = 9.509, $\delta = 2.252$, 95% CI [2.104, 2.401], $p \leq 0.001$) and Congress (OR = 4.961, $\delta = 1.602$, 95% CI

¹⁰This is the very same question tested in the proof-of-concept as ground-truth.

[1.468, 1.735], $p \leq 0.001$) boosted the odds of alignment between synthetic and human responses by 40 and 33 percentage points in F1-score, respectively. On the contrary, Churchillian democracy (OR = 0.466, $\delta = -0.764$, 95% CI [-0.887, -0.641], $p \leq 0.001$) and prospective evaluation of the country’s economic situation (OR = 0.589, $\delta = -0.530$, 95% CI [-0.651, 0.409], $p \leq 0.001$) perform worse than the reference category by 18 and 13 percentage points.

5 Discussion and Limitations

Taking into account our error-rate and bias analyses as evidence to evaluate the similarity of the synthetic sample generated using LLMs compared to actual human survey responses from a probabilistic sample, some takeaways stand out. First, the best models, namely GPT-4o-mini (2024-07-18) and Llama 4 Maverick (400B),¹¹ achieved an acceptable level of performance, indicating limited realism and a need for further improvement. Therefore, these synthetic respondents are able to emulate broad patterns and trends, demonstrating the potential of synthetic sampling as a cost-effective and scalable tool for exploring general attitudes and benchmarking against traditional surveys. Second, though we did not find strong evidence of bias based on sociodemographic differences in the synthetic respondents, we did not test educational or socioeconomic level, which should be evaluated in future iterations of this work.

As limitations, synthetic responses still struggle to capture the nuanced complexity of public opinion, particularly among underrepresented demographic groups, where attempts to approximate minority views can lead to larger errors (Morris, 2025; Santurkar et al., 2023). This outcome is unsurprising and is linked to the complexity of public opinion dynamics. It also relates to the limitations of training data, which may have restricted exposure to local contexts, cultural nuances, and linguistic variations, thereby introducing biases in the representation of specific regions or populations (Qu and Wang, 2024). Moreover, most of the variables we used to elaborate our synthetic profiles could interact in complex, non-linear ways.

Although synthetic samples offer clear advantages in terms of cost, speed, and experimental flexibility, they lack the probabilistic design of survey sampling (Bisbee et al., 2024). Without careful calibration, there is a risk of exaggerating or underrepresenting some trends, jeopardising algorithmic fidelity (Argyle et al., 2023; Ma et al., 2025). For this reason, the primary value of synthetic samples lies, for the moment, in proof-of-concept exercises, sensitivity testing, and trend and complementary analysis, which allow LLMs and surveys to upgrade their capabilities mutually through, for example, alignment

¹¹GPT-4o (2024-11-20) is similar but more expensive.

or fine-tuning (Kim and Lee, 2024).

Considering these results, future avenues for research could involve varying levels of effort and resources, ranging from low to high. First, tuning the prompting strategy would imply a low level of further effort. Second, post-processing work, such as reweighing or calibrating synthetic samples, could be a medium-effort option that would allow reestimating the actual weights of the baseline probabilistic sample and incorporating adjustments based on bias and error-rate analysis of the LLMs. In addition, another medium-effort alternative would be testing some additional recently released models, particularly some reasoning models, however, that could be extremely time-consuming. Lastly, fine-tuning and model alignment would be an excellent alternative and may be the most promising venue, however, it is time-consuming and requires more resources.

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Appendix

Table A.1: Goodness-of-Prediction Indicators of Proof-of-Concept Against Economic Perception Ground-Truth

Model	Prompt	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
GPT-4o-mini (2024-07-18)	Demographics	0.530	0.458	0.530	0.473
	Attitudes	0.553	0.516	0.553	0.517
o1-mini (2024-09-12)	Demographics	0.515	0.498	0.515	0.497
	Attitudes	0.465	0.472	0.465	0.462
o3-mini (2025-01-31)	Demographics	0.534	0.485	0.534	0.486
	Attitudes	0.476	0.467	0.476	0.468
GPT-4o (2024-11-20)	Demographics	0.492	0.481	0.492	0.470
	Attitudes	0.439	0.475	0.439	0.404
GPT-4.5-preview (2025-02-27)	Demographics	0.543	0.462	0.543	0.449
	Attitudes	0.540	0.471	0.540	0.467
GPT-4.1 (2025-04-14)	Demographics	0.539	0.468	0.539	0.416
	Attitudes	0.542	0.465	0.542	0.449
GPT-4.1-mini (2025-04-14)	Demographics	0.540	0.468	0.540	0.431
	Attitudes	0.540	0.473	0.540	0.435
GPT-4.1-nano (2025-04-14)	Demographics	0.471	0.491	0.471	0.477
	Attitudes	0.509	0.519	0.509	0.506
Llama 3.3 (70B)	Demographics	0.533	0.462	0.533	0.476
	Attitudes	0.510	0.476	0.510	0.489
Llama 4 Scout (107B)	Demographics	0.527	0.478	0.527	0.444
	Attitudes	0.512	0.495	0.512	0.491
Llama 4 Maverick (400B)	Demographics	0.530	0.445	0.530	0.443
	Attitudes	0.542	0.479	0.542	0.499
Qwen 2.5 (32B)	Demographics	0.538	0.470	0.538	0.489
	Attitudes	0.527	0.486	0.527	0.505
Gemma 3 (12B)	Demographics	0.540	0.495	0.540	0.394
	Attitudes	0.544	0.472	0.544	0.457

Note. Accuracy reports the proportion of synthetic samples aligned with the probabilistic reference sample. Precision represents the fraction of predicted positives that are correct, and recall indicates the proportion of actual positives identified. The F1-score is the harmonic measure that combines both precision and recall.

Table A.2: Goodness-of-Prediction Indicators of Expanded Ground-Truth Questions for Benchmark – Top 15 Model × Question Pairs

Model	Ground-Truth	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
GPT-4o (2024-11-20)	Trust in political parties	0.940	0.883	0.940	0.911
GPT-4o-mini (2024-07-18)	Trust in political parties	0.940	0.883	0.940	0.911
Llama 4 Maverick (400B)	Trust in political parties	0.940	0.883	0.940	0.911
GPT-4o-mini (2024-07-18)	Trust in Congress	0.893	0.797	0.893	0.842
GPT-4o (2024-11-20)	Trust in Congress	0.893	0.797	0.893	0.842
Llama 4 Maverick (400B)	Trust in Congress	0.822	0.798	0.822	0.807
Qwen 2.5 (32B)	Trust in Congress	0.777	0.797	0.777	0.779
GPT-4o (2024-11-20)	Trust in justice	0.820	0.707	0.820	0.748
Llama 4 Maverick (400B)	Trust in television	0.807	0.716	0.807	0.744
GPT-4o (2024-11-20)	Trust in television	0.821	0.680	0.822	0.744
GPT-4o (2024-11-20)	Trust in government	0.807	0.711	0.807	0.723
Llama 4 Maverick (400B)	Trust in government	0.795	0.695	0.795	0.737
GPT-4o-mini (2024-07-18)	Trust in government	0.778	0.715	0.778	0.732
Qwen 2.5 (32B)	Trust in government	0.758	0.679	0.758	0.712
GPT-4o-mini (2024-07-18)	Trust in television	0.696	0.708	0.696	0.686

Note. Accuracy reports the proportion of synthetic samples aligned with the probabilistic reference sample. Precision represents the fraction of predicted positives that are correct, and recall indicates the proportion of actual positives identified. The F1-score is the harmonic measure that combines both precision and recall.

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